

$n = 0$ (AHCE), 1(AHOP)
 $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$

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References

1. T. R. SEASHADRI and S. VARDARAJAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1952, **35**, 75.
2. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, R. L. GOEL and B. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 958.
3. R. B. ARORA and C. N. MATHAR, *Brst. J. Pharmacol.*, 1963, **20**, 29.
4. C. R. HANCOCK, H. B. BARLOW and H. J. LACEY, *J. Exptl. Bot.*, 1961, **12**, 401.
5. A. RUSSEL and J. R. FRYE, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, **3** 281.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1978, pp. 447, 462, 531.
7. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1089.
8. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
9. Y. INOMATO, T. INOMATO and T. MORIWAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 818.
10. R. L. DUTTA and R. K. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 185.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1970, pp. 159, 167, 214.
12. A. K. RANA and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1100.
13. N. S. BIRADAR, V. B. MOHALE and B. R. HAVINALE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 6.
14. J. OSASZAR and L. KISS, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1978, **78**, 17.
15. K. BURGER, "Coordination Chemistry: Experimental Method", Butterworths, London, 1973, p. 93.
16. N. SONODA and T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 261.
17. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967.
18. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 768.
19. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 87.
20. C. J. BALHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 256.
21. T. S. PIPER and R. L. BELFORD, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, **5**, 169.

Complexes of Rhodium(III) and Palladium(II) with *N*-Vinylimidazole

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IN continuation of our studies on the transition metal complexes of benzimidazole and imidazole derivatives¹⁻⁶ we report herein the complexes of rhodium(III) and palladium(II) with *N*-vinylimidazole (NVIZ). The ligand coordinates as simple imidazole molecule leaving behind the vinyl group (CH=CH) uncoordinated.

Experimental

The reaction of NVIZ (0.004 mol) with an ethanolic solution of rhodium(III) chloride (0.001 mol in 50 ml) at reflux temperature gave cream yellow precipitate of $\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_3\text{Cl}_3$. The product on further refluxing for ~2 h on a steam-bath gave light yellow solution from which cream coloured crystalline precipitate of $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ separated on concentration and cooling. The perchlorate salt $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as cream white crystals on treating the concentrated reaction mixture with an aqueous solution of NaClO_4 .

The dichloro complex underwent substitution reaction with appropriate anions giving $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{CIX}]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_2$ or NCS) or $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$ or I). The diacido complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{X}_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}$ or I) were obtained on refluxing $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ with five-fold excess of KBr/KI in aqueous solution for 2 h. The complexes $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{CIX}]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_2$ or NCS) were obtained on refluxing $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ with three-fold excess of $\text{NaNO}_2/\text{KNCS}$ in aqueous medium for 30 min. The complexes were isolated as crystalline products on concentrating and cooling the refluxates to small volume (yield 60–70%). The perchlorate derivative $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{CIX}]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained as cream coloured crystalline precipitate similar to $[\text{Rh}(\text{NVIZ})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{ClO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Palladium(II) formed tetrakis complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ as well as diacido complexes $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_2$ or NCS). The complex $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ was prepared by refluxing an aqueous ethanolic solution of PdCl_2 (0.002 mol in 50 ml 90% ethanol) with five mole excess of the ligand on a steam-bath. The complex separated on concentration (pH 8). $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was readily formed when aqueous acidic solution of PdCl_2 (pH 2–3) was treated with hot ethanolic solution of ligand in stoichiometric proportion. The product was filtered after digesting it on a steam-bath. The dichloro complex underwent anion replacement reaction forming $[\text{Pd}(\text{NVIZ})_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_2$ or NCS) when refluxed in aqueous suspension with five-fold excess of potassium salt of an appropriate

anion for 2 h. In general, the complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol or cold aqueous ethanol and dried in air. The analytical results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ethanol λ_{max} (ϵ) (nm)
	Metal	N	Halogen	
[RhL ₄ Cl ₂]	21.48 (20.94)	16.81 (17.09)	21.98 (21.64)	400sh ^a
[RhL ₄ Cl ₂]OI	17.28 (17.57)	18.81 (19.13)	17.87 (18.17)	235 410 (76)
[RhL ₄ Cl ₂ ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O]	15.13 (15.42)	16.57 (16.78)	—	235 410 (73)
[RhL ₄ Br ₂]Br	14.01 (14.31)	15.31 (15.58)	32.81 (33.35)	320sh 425 (116)
[RhL ₄ I ₂]I	11.62 (11.97)	13.30 (13.02)	44.57 (44.28)	290 390 (9 200) 442sh
[RhL ₄ Cl(NCS)]NOS	15.92 (16.32)	21.91 (21.20)	—	—
[RhL ₄ Cl(NCS)]ClO ₄ ·H ₂ O	14.61 (14.91)	18.04 (18.26)	—	—
[RhL ₄ Cl(NO ₂)]NO ₂	16.65 (16.67)	23.26 (23.08)	5.61	—
[RhL ₄ Cl(NO ₂)]ClO ₄	15.31 (15.59)	18.72 (19.09)	—	—
[PdL ₄]Cl ₂	19.46 (19.23)	20.08 (20.24)	12.62 (12.81)	232s 350sh
[PdL ₄]Cl ₂	29.00 (29.12)	15.20 (15.32)	19.22 (19.40)	235s 360sh
[PdL ₄]Br ₂	23.20 (23.42)	12.06 (12.32)	34.78 (35.18)	232s 370sh
[PdI ₄]I ₂	19.65 (19.40)	10.03 (10.21)	45.89 (46.29)	230, 295 360s, 445sh
[PdL ₄ (NCS) ₂]	26.00 (25.92)	19.98 (20.46)	—	230sh 340sh
PdL ₄ (NO ₂) ₂	27.13 (27.53)	21.43 (21.73)	—	215s 280sh

* L = NVIz. ^a Reflectance band.

Results and Discussion

The hydrated complexes become anhydrous below 100° indicating that H₂O is not coordinated to metal atom. The tetrakis complex salts of both Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} are soluble in ethanol or aqueous ethanol whereas other complexes have poor solubility. At room temperature (30–2°), the DMF solution of [Pd(NVIz)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br, I, NCS or NO₂) and [Rh(NVIz)₃Cl₃] show negligible electric conductance value (4–9 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm²) indicating their non-electrolytic nature. [Pd(NVIz)₄]Cl₂ and diacido complex salts of Rh^{III} display conductance value of ~158 and 81–93 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm², which occur in the expected range of 1:2 and 1:1 electrolytes, respectively¹¹. In general, the complexes are diamagnetic suggesting six-coordinated octahedral geometry for Rh^{III} and four coordinated square planar geometry for Pd^{II} complexes.

The electronic absorption spectrum of NVIz shows a strong band at 212 nm and a shoulder at 320 nm in ethanol. In complexes, the former is shifted between 215 and 235 nm while the latter is usually enveloped in charge transfer band.

Palladium(II) complexes shows reflectance band as shoulder in the range of 340–440 nm assignable to ¹A_{1g}→^B_{1g} transition¹². [Pd(NVIz)₂I₂] shows two additional strong bands at 360 and 295 nm attributable to charge transfer transitions^{12,13}. The reflectance spectrum of [Rh(NVIz)₃Cl₃] displays a ligand field band at 400 nm assignable to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} transition in octahedral field^{14,15}. The absorption spectra of complex salts of [Rh(NVIz)₄X₂]⁻ (X = Cl, Br or I) show two ligand field transitions in the regions 410–442 and ~320 nm assignable to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} and ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{1g}+ligand molecule absorptions, respectively. The nature of absorption and the ϵ_{max} value of Rh^{III} complexes (Table 1) are similar to *trans*-Rh^{III} complexes¹⁶ and therefore *trans*-structure is tentatively suggested to them.

The ν_{C-H} and $\nu_{C=C}$ of vinyl group (3 080 and 1 630 cm⁻¹) of NVIz are not shifted to lower frequency in the ir spectra of the complexes, suggesting that CH₂=CH group is not involved in coordination. In complexes, the ν_{C-N} of the ligand (1595 cm⁻¹) is shifted to lower wave number by 5–10 cm⁻¹ indicating that imidazole pyridine nitrogen is bonded to the metal atom¹⁷. [Rh(NVIz)₄ClNO₂]ClO₄·H₂O displays $\nu_{as}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1 418, $\nu_s(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1 332 and δ_{ONO} at 822 cm⁻¹ similar to N-bonded *trans*-NO₂ group^{18,19}. The broad and strong (ClO₄) and at 1 110–1 080 cm⁻¹ supports the ionic character of ClO₄⁻ in [Rh(NVIz)₄Cl(NO₂)]·ClO₄·H₂O. The ir spectra of [Rh(NVIz)₄Cl(NCS)]·ClO₄·H₂O reveal $\nu_{C=N}$ as strong and broad band at 2 112 cm⁻¹ and δ_{NCS} at 506 cm⁻¹, suggesting N-bonding of NCS in the complex²⁰.

The ir spectra of [Pd(NVIz)₂(NO₂)₂] show $\nu_{as}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1 392s br cm⁻¹ and ν_s at 1 327 cm⁻¹ while δ_{ONO} at 818 cm⁻¹ suggesting the N-bonding of nitrogroup in *trans* position¹⁹. The spectra of thiocyanate complex [Pd(NVIz)₂(SCN)₂] show $\nu_{C=N}$ band as sharp and strong band at 2 104 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{C=S}$ at 700 cm⁻¹, suggesting the coordination of thiocyanate group through sulphur atom²⁰. No splitting of ν_{C-N} or δ_{ONO} vibrations could be observed, indicating that thiocyanate and nitro group are coordinated in *trans*-position in Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} complexes^{19,20}.

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References

1. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chm. Acta*, 1973, 7, 545.
2. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1153.
3. S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 308.
4. S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE, L. DUBEY and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 230.

5. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **59**, 212.
6. W. J. EILBECK, F. HOLMS and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1967, 759.
7. W. J. DAVIS and J. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1974, 317.
8. K. J. REEDIS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **3**, 617.
9. C. D. BURBRIDGE and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **4**, 231.
10. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 480.
11. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, S. FRAZ, D. T. PHILLIPS and S. Y. TYREE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3770.
12. W. ROY MASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5221.
13. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
14. J. SCHERZER, P. PHILLIPS, L. OLAPP and J. EDWARDS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 847.
15. H. H. SCHMIDTKE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1965, **339**, 103.
16. A. W. ADDISON, K. DAWSON, R. D. GILLARD, B. T. HEATON and H. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 589.
17. N. S. GILL, R. H. NATTALL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
18. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1967, pp. 167, 173.
19. B. M. GATHOUSE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 79.
20. J. L. BURMIESTER and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.* 1964, **3**, 1587.

Synthesis and Characterisation of Lanthanide(III) Perrhenate Adducts of *N,N'*-Dioxides of 1,10-Phenanthroline and 2,2'-Bipyridine

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THE synthesis of lanthanide(III) perrhenate adducts with 1,10-phenanthroline *N,N'*-dioxide (PhenNO₂) and 2,2'-bipyridine *N,N'*-dioxide (BipyNO₂) is reported in this communication.

Experimental

The hydrated lanthanide(III) perrhenates were obtained by reaction of dilute perrhenic acid and lanthanide basic carbonate¹. The ligands PhenNO₂ and BipyNO₂ were prepared from 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridine, respectively, as reported earlier^{2,3}. All the adducts were isolated by the following general method. Lanthanide(III) perrhenate (1 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of ethanol (10 ml) and 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (5 ml) and refluxed for 15 min. The mixture was treated with a solution of the ligand (2.25 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml). The complexes separated on cooling were washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses, conductance and magnetic susceptibilities of the newly synthesised complexes were determined as before^{4,5}. All the complexes have the general composition Ln(ReO₄)₃.2L (Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho or Yb; L = PhenNO₂ or BipyNO₂). The complexes were slightly hygroscopic. The molar conductivity values in nitromethane in the range 91.6–98.9 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggest that they behave as 1 : 1 electrolyte⁶. The magnetic moment values of lanthanide(III) complexes (Table 1) show a slight deviation from the Van Vleck values^{7,8}, thereby indicating that 4f-electrons do not take part in bond formation in these compounds.

The ir spectra of all the complexes were similar showing no significant dependence on the central metal ion. In free ligand, ν_{N-O} at 1 312 and 1 282 cm⁻¹ (in the case of PhenNO₂)^{9,10} and 1 264 and 1 260 cm⁻¹ (for BipyNO₂)¹¹ shifted to lower frequencies upon complex formation indicating O,O-chelation by PhenNO₂ and BipyNO₂ in these complexes¹². Slight shift of the NO bending band (855–840 cm⁻¹) provides further supports oxygen linkage between metal and the ligands. In the far-ir region (410–385 cm⁻¹), metal–ligand vibrations have been identified.

The complexes behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes, thus it may be suggestive that the complexes contain ionic as well as covalent ReO₄⁻ ions. The strong band (ν₈) at ~900 cm⁻¹ observed for perrhenate indicate that T_d symmetry of this ion is maintained and it is not coordinated to the tripositive lantha-

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC MOMENT (μ_{eff}, B.M.) VALUES OF COMPLEXES AT 303 K

Ln	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Yb
Ln(ReO ₄) ₃ .2PhenNO ₂	Diamag	2.54	3.60	3.58	1.61	7.90	9.90	10.47	10.48	4.25
Ln(ReO ₄) ₃ .2BipyNO ₂	Diamag.	2.56	3.64	3.56	1.59	7.91	9.29	10.45	10.47	4.26